

Improving reading skills through effective strategies

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Annotation

This article explores the importance of effective strategies in developing students' reading skills. It focuses on cognitive and metacognitive approaches, highlighting strategies such as predicting, questioning, visualizing, and summarizing to improve text comprehension. The role of the teacher, individualized instruction, and consistent practice are also discussed. The findings indicate that the systematic use of these strategies enhances both reading speed and comprehension.

Keywords: reading skills, effective strategies, cognitive approach, metacognitive approach, text comprehension.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada o'quvchilarning o'qish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda samarali strategiyalarning ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Unda kognitiv va metakognitiv yondashuvlar asosida predicting, questioning, visualizing hamda summarizing kabi strategiyalarning matni anglash jarayonidagi o'rnini yoritiladi. Shuningdek, o'qituvchining yo'naltiruvchi roli, individual yondashuv va muntazam mashg'ulotlarning samaradorligi ko'rsatib o'tiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari ushbu strategiyalarni tizimli qo'llash o'qish tezligi va tushunish darajasini oshirishini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qish ko'nikmasi, samarali strategiyalar, kognitiv yondashuv, metakognitiv yondashuv, matni tushunish.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается значение эффективных стратегий в развитии навыков чтения у учащихся. Освещаются когнитивные и метакогнитивные подходы, а также такие стратегии, как прогнозирование, постановка вопросов, визуализация и обобщение, способствующие пониманию текста. Отмечается роль учителя, индивидуальный подход и регулярная практика. Результаты показывают, что систематическое применение данных стратегий повышает скорость чтения и уровень понимания текста.

Ключевые слова: навыки чтения, эффективные стратегии, когнитивный подход, метакогнитивный подход, понимание текста.

Good readers are actively involved with the text, and they are aware of the processes they use to understand what they read. Teachers can help improve student comprehension through instruction of reading strategies. Predicting, making connections, visualizing, inferring, questioning, and summarizing are strategies shown by research to improve reading comprehension (Block & Israel, 2005). It is important to teach the strategies by naming the strategy and how it should be used, modelling through the think-aloud process, group practice, partner practice, and independent use of the strategy (Duke & Pearson, 2005).

Predicting. In order to be a good reader, learners should set a goal for their reading; therefore good readers have a purpose for reading. One strategy for improving comprehension is predicting, which helps the reader set a purpose for their reading. Research has shown that good readers use their experiences and knowledge to make predictions and formulate ideas as they read. This strategy also allows for more student interaction, which increases student interest and improves their understanding of the text. It is important to compare the outcome in the actual text with the prediction process as it will lead the learner to improve his understanding. Without this aspect of prediction process, it becomes meaningless to improve the student's comprehension. Some of the

approaches for teaching predicting are teacher modeling, predicting throughout the text; with partners, with a graphic organizer, or using post-it notes throughout the text. Using the title, table of contents, pictures, and key words is one prediction strategy. Another key prediction strategy is to have students predict at specific points through the text, evaluate the prediction, and revise predictions if necessary.

Visualizing. Another strategy that the good readers employ when comprehending a text is visualization. Visualization requires the reader to construct an image of what is read. This image is stored in the reader's memory as a representation of a reader's interpretation of the text.

Teachers can motivate students to visualize settings, characters, and actions in a story and ask them to make drawings or write about the image that come to their minds after visualizing the text.

Making Connections. Making connections is another strategy that can be used in the reading process. By making connections, the learners can activate their prior knowledge and connect the ideas in the text to their own experiences. Reading becomes meaningful when the reader connects the ideas in the text to their experiences and beliefs, and the things happening in the outer world.

Text-to-Self: Refers to connections made between the text and the reader's personal experience. Text-to-Text: Refers to connections made between a text being read to a text that was previously read. Text-to-World: Refers to connections made between a text being read and something that occurs in the world.

Students can make text-to-text connections through drawing, making a chart, writing, and graphic organizers. These text-to-text connections could be based upon how characters in the story relate to each other, or how story elements relate between stories. Students can make text-to-world connections through drawing, making a chart, writing, or graphic organizers. Text-to-world connections could be done by comparing

characters in a story to characters today or comparing the content of the text to the world today. Giving a purpose to students' reading by asking them to find connections would help them comprehend the ideas better in the text.

Summarizing. The process of summarization requires the reader to determine what is important when reading and to condense the information in the readers own words (Adler, 2001). During the summarizing process, the students will be able to distinguish the main ideas from the supporting ideas. Distinguishing the related knowledge from the unrelated ones is another point in the summarizing process which will help the students' capacity to improve text comprehension. Summarizing is a strategy which helps the students to organize the ideas even in the long reading passages which are usually perceived as threat for the students.

Questioning. Readers can use the questioning before, during, and after reading. The questioning process requires readers to ask questions of themselves to construct meaning, enhance understanding, find answers, solve problems, find information, and discover new information. In this strategy, the students return to the text throughout the reading process to find the answers to the questions asked by the teacher before, during and after the reading. By this strategy, students practice to distinguish between questions that are factual, inferred, or based on reader's prior knowledge. By using the student generated questioning strategy; text segments are integrated and thereby improve reading comprehension

Inferring. Inferring refers to reading between the lines. Students need to use their own knowledge along with information from the text to draw their own conclusions. Through inferring students will be able to draw conclusions, make predictions, identify underlying themes, use information to create meaning from text, and use pictures to create meaning. Students can be given techniques to use illustrations, graphs, pictures, dates, related vocabulary and titles from the text to make inferences.

Conclusion. Reading is a skill that will empower everyone who learns it. They will be able to benefit from the store of knowledge in printed materials and, ultimately, to contribute to that knowledge. Good teaching enables students to learn to read and read to learn. The role of the teacher in the teaching-reading process should be of a companion rather than the boss. Teaching can be interesting and innovative if the efforts are put in to make learning an enjoyable experience.

Successful teaching is where effective learning takes place with the use of appropriate knowledge, the right emotion and accurate application of scientific devices. With consistent progress in science and technology and other areas of study, it is the duty of the teacher to adopt the best methods and employ the best devices to ensure rapid growth in the teaching process. Teachers must be aware of the progress that students are making and adjust instruction to the changing abilities of students. Both research and classroom practices support the use of a balanced approach in instruction. Because reading depends on efficient word recognition and comprehension, instruction should develop reading skills and strategies, as well as build on learners' knowledge through the use of authentic texts. Similarly, the most effective way of dealing with the problem of cultural meaning in texts is to encourage students to read by themselves, choosing subjects related initially to their own interests so that they bring motivation and experience to reading. As their understanding of other cultures and of unfamiliar views increases through reading, they will bring to their reading activities a gradually increasing capacity to understand the full meaning of texts.

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